

FL-DApp: Open-source decentralized application for reputation in O-RAN federated learning

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ABSTRACT

Operational Federated Learning (FL) across multiple operators in Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) settings demands trustworthy coordination. We introduce FL-DApp, a blockchain-based, open-source Decentralized Application (DApp) for lightweight, reputation-driven client selection. Aligned with the O-RAN architecture, FL-DApp exposes a minimal, portable on-chain interface on Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM) networks, supported by off-chain adapters that (i) register participants, (ii) collect and verify per-round validation metrics, and (iii) compute and store reputations. Model training and aggregation remain off-chain to minimize computational overhead. To support reproducibility and adoption, FL-DApp includes a scriptable workflow and generates structured outputs and CSV logs. The reference implementation targets the Polygon Amoy testnet and is portable across EVM-compatible layers. We evaluate registration, metric submission, reputation update, and finalization under realistic conditions. Around 86% of batched reputation commits are confirmed within seven seconds, enabling seconds-scale cycles aligned with the non-real-time RAN Intelligent Controller (Non-RT RIC) in the Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) framework. FL-DApp thus offers a practical and reproducible foundation for transparent, decentralized FL in multi-operator O-RAN environments.

Code metadata

Code metadata description	Metadata
Current code version	v1.0.0
Permanent link to code/repository used for this code version	https://github.com/farhanajaved/SoftX-FL-DAPP
Permanent link to reproducible capsule	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17492203
Legal code license	MIT License
Code versioning system used	Git
Software code languages, tools, and services used	Solidity; JavaScript/TypeScript; Python; Node.js ≥ 18; Hardhat 2.22.x; Ethers.js v6; dotenv; Chainlink contracts v0.8
Compilation requirements, operating environments, and dependencies	Linux; Node.js ≥ 18; RPC endpoint (e.g., Alchemy); Polygon Amoy testnet; Chainlink node/mock
If available, link to developer documentation/manual	README with deployment & usage examples
Support email for questions	farhana.javed@cttc.es

1. Motivation and significance

The evolution toward 5G and beyond demands flexible, interoperable, and software-defined radio access. Open Radio Access Network

(O-RAN) addresses this by disaggregating traditional RAN into virtualized, programmable components (O-RU, O-DU, O-CU), enabling multi-vendor integration, rapid innovation, and cost efficiency via white-box hardware [1–3]. O-RAN promotes openness and embedded intelligence

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by decoupling functions from proprietary stacks and integrating AI/ML for analysis, decision automation, and performance optimization with minimal operator intervention [4–7].

As AI/ML adoption grows across providers, centralized learning becomes impractical due to privacy, regulatory, and competitive constraints. Federated Learning (FL) addresses this by training models locally and exchanging updates, enabling tasks like resource prediction and anomaly detection without sharing raw data [4,5,7,8]. However, FL lacks native mechanisms for cross-domain trust: adversarial or low-quality updates can impair model integrity, with no auditable means to validate or exclude participants. A decentralized trust layer is essential [9–11]. Blockchain provides a tamper-evident foundation, enforcing logic through smart contracts. Telecom standards bodies (e.g., TM Forum, CAMARA, ETSI PDL) are actively investigating blockchain for secure multi-domain coordination [12–16].

We consider a standard FL setting in which multiple operators collaboratively train a shared model without exchanging raw data [5]. Each Client Service Provider (CLSP) i retains its local dataset and performs local training to update a global model broadcast by an Aggregator Service Provider (AGSP). After each round, the AGSP aggregates client updates or validation metrics into a new global model, typically using variants of FedAvg or weighted aggregation over client contributions [7,8]. In this work, model training and aggregation remain within the SMO/Non-RT RIC domain. FL-DApp adds a transparent reputation layer that records signed validation metrics and reputation scores on chain, without modifying the underlying FL algorithms.

This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews related work; Section 3 describes the software architecture; Section 4 details the workflow and smart-contract logic; Section 5 presents illustrative runs and evaluation; Section 6 discusses impact; and Section 7 concludes.

2. Related work

Blockchain has been widely combined with FL to provide a decentralized, tamper-evident record of contributions and outcomes,

Table 1
Related work on blockchain-enabled reputation mechanisms.

Ref.	Scope	Blockchain deployment	Reputation model	Reusable artifact	Limitations
[17]	Healthcare FL with incentive-based reputation.	Permissioned RPBFT chain (no public net).	On-chain multidimensional reputation and token rewards.	×	Vertical-specific; permissioned only; no open EVM artifact or gas/latency logs.
[18]	Crowdsourcing with privacy-preserving worker reputation.	Hyperledger Fabric (permissioned).	On-chain reputation via commitments and signatures.	×	Fabric-specific prototype; no EVM stack or public-chain performance study.
[19]	Auditable FL with trust and incentives.	Custom PoD blockchain (non-EVM).	On-chain tracking of FL contributions and rewards.	×	Protocol-focused; no reusable EVM contracts or public PoS deployment/tooling.
[20]	Credible blockchain-based FL with malicious model detection.	Smart-contract system (platform abstracted).	Contracts for model submission, attack detection, and credit.	×	Mainly architectural; no open contracts, public testnet deployment, or gas/latency metrics.
[21]	FL worker selection via improved reputation evaluation.	Blockchain with PoT-style consensus.	Direct/indirect reputation with time windows.	×	Improved selection logic, but no modular stack or public-chain evaluation.
[22]	Marketplace trust/reputation (no FL).	Smart-contract reputation layer (public/consortium).	Time-discounted trust; Sybil resistance.	×	Generic marketplace setting; no FL/O-RAN workflow or FL-specific artifact.
[23]	Decentralized FL with reputation-based leader election (no blockchain).	No ledger; fully off-chain.	Reputation-driven leader election with SNIPs.	×	Ledger-free design; no on-chain state, smart contracts, or blockchain metrics.
[24]	Scalable reputation-aware decentralized FL.	EVM Layer 1 + zk-rollup Layer 2 (research PoC).	Automated, incentive-oriented reputation aggregated in L2.	×	Protocol PoC; no O-RAN workflow or packaged DApp toolkit for public testnets.
[25]	Verifiable privacy-preserving BFL.	Blockchain verifying zk-SNARK/IVC proofs.	On-chain proof checking of training/aggregation (no long-term scores).	×	Cryptography-centric; no multi-round on-chain reputation, O-RAN focus, or reusable EVM deployment scripts.
FL-DApp (this work)	O-RAN-oriented FL with blockchain-based reputation.	EVM-compatible Polygon Amoy PoS public testnet.	Off-chain per-round scores; on-chain batched updates.	✓	Open-source EVM contracts and scripts; public and live PoS evaluation with gas/latency metrics (up to 50 clients).

reducing reliance on centralized orchestrators [26–30]. Reputation mechanisms naturally complement this setting by summarizing client reliability from past behavior and contribution quality [31–33]. Table 1 summarizes frameworks that couple blockchain, FL, and reputation and contrasts them with FL-DApp across software and deployment aspects. Prior work covers incentive-aware healthcare FL, privacy-preserving crowdsourcing, and scalable/verifiable BFL [17–21,24,25]. While these systems study incentives, malicious update filtering, and advanced consensus/proof mechanisms, they often assume permissioned or bespoke infrastructures, prioritize protocol design over reusable artifacts, and rarely provide EVM-compatible contracts and scripts deployable on public PoS testnets.

Related efforts also study reputation and hybrid on/off-chain computation outside FL (e.g., marketplace trust services, off-chain reputation-aware FL, rollup-based reputation) [22,23,34–36]. Open-source blockchain-enabled FL frameworks and simulators exist for protocol exploration [37–39], but they are not O-RAN-oriented reputation services and typically lack (i) a minimal round-batched reputation contract, (ii) integration with SMO/Non-RT RIC workflows, and (iii) scripted evaluations on live PoS testnets with structured gas/latency logs. FL-DApp targets this gap by providing an open-source, O-RAN-oriented reputation DApp with minimal on-chain state, off-chain round-batched scoring, and reproducible evaluation on the Polygon Amoy PoS testnet under realistic fees and congestion. It is designed to plug into existing FL pipelines as a lightweight, auditable trust layer rather than a full FL protocol, while exposing concrete gas and latency traces from a live public network.

3. Software description and architecture

In Fig. 1, we introduce an O-RAN Machine Learning (ML) framework augmented with a lightweight blockchain-based trust layer to enable auditability in multi-vendor environments. The system supports flexible ML host placement across the Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) framework, including the Non-Real-Time (Non-RT) and Near-Real-Time (Near-RT) RAN Intelligent Controllers (RICs) [4,5,40].

Fig. 1. System architecture highlighting FL-DApp components.

```

1 event ClientRegistered(address indexed client);
2
3 mapping(address => bool) private registeredClients;
4
5 function registerAsClient() external {
6     require(!registeredClients[msg.sender], "ALREADY_CLIENT"); // rejects
7     ↪ duplicates
8     registeredClients[msg.sender] = true;
9     emit ClientRegistered(msg.sender);
10 }
11
12 function isClient(address a) external view returns (bool) {
13     return registeredClients[a];
14 }

```

Listing 1. Client registration.

Following the MonB5G CPU prediction use case [41],¹ we adopt *Option 3*, placing the *FL Training Host* in the SMO and the *FL Inference Host* in the Non-RT RIC, aligned with non-real-time control loops.

Two service provider roles participate: each with an *SMO Client* that trains locally and executes inference, and an *AGSP* with an *SMO Aggregator* that coordinates rounds and performs global aggregation. A trust layer records accuracy scores [31] and maintains per-client reputation [14,16]. FL-DApp wraps a conventional round-based FL loop. At the start of round r , the AGSP holds the current global model and broadcasts it to all CLSPs via the SMO. Each CLSP performs local training on its own MonB5G-derived dataset and runs inference at the Non-RT RIC to compute a validation metric (NMSE). The Oracle Adapter then signs and forwards this metric to the blockchain layer, where `performanceSubmission` stores a single fixed-point value per $(\text{client}, \text{roundId})$. The AGSP's off-chain Reputation Manager retrieves these metrics, computes reputation scores, selects eligible clients according to the configured policy, and triggers the next aggregation step using the selected clients' local models. The resulting updated reputation snapshot is then committed to the chain via `updateScore()` and sealed with `finalizeRound()`, providing an auditable record of how FL decisions are informed by reputation.

Following the architecture in [42], we document FL-DApp as a reusable artifact and summarize the implementation of smart contracts,

off-chain orchestration, and reputation processing, emphasizing modularity and reproducibility. (i) The SMO-Client provides an Oracle Adapter to sign Non-RT RIC inference metrics and a DApp Adapter for blockchain I/O (registration, submission, policy queries), including nonce management, gas estimation, and retries. (ii) The blockchain layer includes an Access Control Manager (ACM) for authorisation and a Smart Contract Orchestrator (SCO) exposing `openRound`, `closeRound`, `submitNMSE`, `finalizeRound`, and `setOracle`. Contracts store fixed-point metrics, round flags, and reputation scores; model artifacts remain off-chain. (iii) The SMO-Aggregator subscribes to validated metrics, manages round state, and includes a Reputation Manager (weights) plus a Reputation Cache to reduce read overhead. RIC interfaces (O1/A1) are outside the trust layer. Appendix C Table 2 lists core entry points. Training data comes from a 5G video-streaming testbed (MonB5G) [41], using CSV for data and YAML/JSON for configuration to ensure portability. The dataset spans M clients; each client i stores time-stamped CPU and traffic records (median N samples/client).

4. Software functionality and workflow

4.1. Registration

Identity and role management are centralized in `registrationClient`, which exposes `CLIENT_ROLE` and `AGGREGATOR_ROLE`. Authorisation is enforced in the SCO via read-only guards (e.g., `isClient(addr)`, `isAggregator(addr)`): performance submission requires `CLIENT_ROLE` (see Listing 1), while round-control functions require `AGGREGATOR_ROLE`.

¹ <https://www.monb5g.eu/>, accessed October 2025.

```

1 event PerformanceSubmitted(address indexed client, uint32 indexed roundId,
   ↪ uint256 nmseFixed);
2
3 function submitNMSE(uint32 roundId, uint256 nmseFixed) external {
4     // guards elided: onlyOracle (forwarded by fetchOracle), client role,
   ↪ round open, TTL/freshness, scale check
5     roundPerformance[roundId][msg.sender] = nmseFixed; // single effective
   ↪ value
6     emit PerformanceSubmitted(msg.sender, roundId, nmseFixed);
7 }

```

Listing 2. Core submission path.

These views are invoked by the SCO to gate `submitNMSE` (via `isClient`) and to authorise round-control calls by the AGSP (via `isAggregator`), ensuring only registered principals can progress state.

4.2. Performance submission

Performance evidence crosses the trust boundary via an Oracle Adapter that signs payloads; the `fetchOracle` validates the signature, role membership, and freshness prior to forwarding. On-chain acceptance is conditioned on correctness (the writer holds `CLIENT_ROLE` and the target round is *Open*), freshness (the timestamp is within `ttlSec` and strictly newer for the same `(client, roundId)`), and minimality (the chain stores fixed-point references and round flags only). The SCO therefore maintains a single effective value per client and round and emits typed events. Each client computes NMSE off-chain during the inference step on its local held-out validation window by comparing the model's predicted CPU-load time series against the corresponding ground-truth measurements, following the MonB5G evaluation setup [41].

For on-chain compatibility, NMSE is quantised as:

$$\text{nmse_fixed} = \lfloor \text{NMSE} \cdot 10^6 \rfloor, \quad \text{scale} = 10^6$$

and carried with `roundId`, timestamp, and feed reference in the signed payload (see Listing 2 below).

Payloads conform to the oracle schema and are forwarded with a provider signature:

```

1 {"client_id":"0xAbC...123", "round":0, "ts":1750000000,
   ↪ "nmse_fixed":25341, "scale":1000000}

```

```

1 requests.post(ORACLE_ADAPTER_URL, json=payload,
   ↪ timeout=10).raise_for_status()

```

The relevant SCO write interfaces are listed in Table 3; models and aggregates remain off-chain to minimise footprint.

4.3. Reputation update

Reputation is computed off chain by the AGSP from oracle-validated metrics and committed on chain as a round-scoped snapshot. Let $i \in \{1, \dots, M\}$ index the registered clients and let r denote the FL round. We write $\text{nmse}_i^{(r)}$ for the scalar NMSE value reported by client i at round r . The Reputation Manager maps this metric to an integer reputation score $\text{score}_i^{(r)}$ using a monotone inverse-NMSE rule:

$$\text{score}_i^{(r)} = \left\lfloor \frac{\alpha}{\text{nmse}_i^{(r)} + \epsilon} \right\rfloor, \quad \alpha = 10^{18}, \epsilon > 0,$$

Here, α is a fixed scaling constant chosen to fit within the `uint256` fixed-point range used on-chain, and ϵ is a small positive constant that prevents division by zero and caps the maximum score when $\text{nmse}_i^{(r)}$ is

very small. In our implementation, ϵ is set in the same fixed-point domain as `nmse_fixed` (scale 10^6); we use $\epsilon = 10$ (i.e., $10/10^6$ in the original NMSE scale), which only affects the near-zero edge case and is negligible for typical NMSE values. Lower NMSE therefore results in higher reputation scores. The resulting fixed-point integer scores are then written to the contract via `updateScore(roundId, clients[], scores[])` and sealed for each round by `finalizeRound()`. This scoring and selection logic is executed once per FL round. For M registered clients, the off-chain computation of $\text{score}_i^{(r)}$ is $O(M)$, with at most $O(M \log M)$ overhead if a full ranking is required. The on-chain batched `updateScore()` call performs a single linear pass over the cohort. Over R FL rounds, the reputation therefore scales as $O(RM)$ while still requiring only one reputation transaction per round. The gas usage and latency of the corresponding on-chain calls are reported in Section 5.3.

FL-DApp does not require all registered clients to participate in every round. Let $\mathcal{A}^{(r)} \subseteq \{1, \dots, M\}$ denote the set of clients that successfully submit a valid NMSE value in round r via the oracle. The Reputation Manager computes scores only for clients in $\mathcal{A}^{(r)}$ and calls `updateScore(roundId, clients[], scores[])` with the corresponding addresses and scores. Clients that are offline in round r simply do not appear in this batch, and their previously finalized reputation remains stored on chain so they can rejoin in later rounds. It produces fixed-point integer scores that are persisted via `updateScore` and sealed by `finalizeRound`. Only clients in $\mathcal{A}^{(r)}$ that submit NMSE in round r are included in the `updateScore(...)` batch; non-participating clients retain their last *finalized* on-chain reputation.

Preconditions and state effects for reputation functions are summarised in Table 4; the public interface and guard checks are in Appendix A (Listings 4–5). During aggregation, an ephemeral reputation cache maintained by the AGSP may reduce read amplification; the cache is invalidated on `closeRound` and reconciled against the finalized on-chain snapshot (see Listing 3).

FL-DApp keeps the on-chain ABI minimal: contracts store only round flags, fixed-point performance metrics, and per-client reputation scores, without hard-coded update rules. Scoring and selection policies (such as multi-metric, decayed, threshold-weighted, or stake-weighted reputation) are implemented entirely in the AGSP's off-chain Reputation Manager, which filters clients and commits the resulting scores via `updateScore()`. Policy parameters such as `selectPct` and `policyHash` are passed through `openRound()` and can be reinterpreted without redeploying contracts. Privacy enhancements are attached at the oracle boundary, where the Oracle Adapter can apply secure aggregation, differential privacy, or zero-knowledge proofs before forwarding metrics, leaving the rest of the FL-DApp workflow unchanged. Client selection can be performed at each training round based on reputation. In our implementation, the selection cutoff is a configurable training-policy parameter, decided off-chain by the AGSP SMO within the Reputation Manager.

Fig. 2 outlines the FL-DApp lifecycle from client registration and training to oracle-backed submission and reputation update. The round-scoped update semantics (active set $\mathcal{A}^{(r)}$ and non-participant persistence) are described in Section 4.3. Role checks and bounded

```

1 // inverse-NMSE fixed-point score and 90% cutoff (M clients)
2 uint score = 1e18 / (nmseValues[i] + epsilon);
3 uint cutoff = totalClients * 90 / 100; // top-90% selection
    
```

Listing 3. Core scoring and selection.

Fig. 2. Sequence diagram of the FL-DApp workflow.

writes ensure auditability, and Fig. 3 shows contract-level module interactions.

5. Illustrative examples

5.1. Deploying and running the FL-DApp

Table 5 also lists the key artifacts and configuration. We deploy the SCO contracts (Section 4) on Polygon Amoy (via Alchemy RPC), bind the Oracle Adapter to `fetchOracle`, open a round on `performanceSubmission`, and stream fixed-point NMSE from SMO clients. The AGSP’s Reputation Manager listens for `PerformanceSubmitted` events, computes scores, and commits a round snapshot via `reputationCalculation`. In our evaluation runs, we configure all registered clients to participate in each round; that is, the active client set $\mathcal{A}^{(r)}$ equals $\{1, \dots, M\}$. When participation is intermittent, $\mathcal{A}^{(r)}$ contains only those clients that submit a valid NMSE value in round r , and the same scoring and update logic applies, with both off-chain computation and the on-chain batched write scaling with the size of $|\mathcal{A}^{(r)}|$. Console output includes contract addresses, registration gas/latency ($\sim 43,464$ gas, 9–10 s; pilot run), and metric submissions. For comparison, later Amoy runs show a per-transaction median of $\sim 193k$ gas (see Section 5.3). We repeat each run (50 clients \times 10 passes) for statistical insight. See Appendix A, Listing 5 for `updateScore()` guard checks.

5.2. Running the FL-DApp

A sample is in Appendix B, Listing 10. Deployment, metric submission, and round finalization are presented in Appendix B, Listing 6. Console output reports client addresses, registration gas/latency, and

Fig. 3. Class diagram of the FL-DApp smart contracts.

submissions as `(client, roundId, nmseFixed, scale, ts)`. We ran 10 full registration iterations; Appendix B Listing 7 reports per-client results, with a median registration latency of 9.55 s [42].

5.3. Live dashboard and on-chain performance

Fig. 4 links the Alchemy dashboard to mined transactions and blocks. We compute inclusion delay with a helper script (Appendix B, Listing 9) that logs sent/mined timestamps and derives per-transaction delay (s). Appendix B Listing 8 reports Broadcast Time, `MINED` status, hash, mempool delay, nonce, effective gas (Gwei), and `Block#`. From these logs, users can compute time-to-mine (mempool delay), link bursts to `Block#`, and estimate cost as $C = \text{gasUsed} \times \text{effectiveGasPrice}$. Over the capture window, `registerAsClient()` is light, `submitNMSE()` moderate, and `updateScore()` heavy; variance reflects bursty load and changing mempool conditions [42].

Fig. 5 plots the ECDF of end-to-end latency for the *single* batched on-chain update that commits all clients’ reputation scores. We observe $\approx 86\%$ of rounds confirming within 7s, with only a small uplift to $\approx 90\%$ by 10 s. We therefore adopt a 7 s service-level objective (SLO) and use 10 s as a conservative upper reference. This latency aligns with the Non-RT RIC’s role in the O-RAN AI/ML framework, which handles non-time-critical training and inference [4,5,40]. In particular, our setup corresponds to Option 3, where the ML Training Host resides in the SMO, and the ML Inference Host in the Non-RT RIC [41]. This deployment suits management tasks with seconds-level responsiveness, as is typical for analytics and policy updates [43,44]. From a platform perspective, Polygon

Fig. 4. Alchemy metrics dashboard for the FL DApp.

Fig. 5. Latency SLO reliability for batched reputation commits.

PoS targets ~2s blocks and 2–3 blocks (6–8 s) are commonly treated as sufficient confirmation [45,46], while Ethereum PoS uses 12 s slots [47]. Hence, our 7 s SLO aligns with observed reliability (86% confirmed) and non-real-time telecom workflows.

6. Impact

FL-DApp builds on established EVM contract and decentralized reputation design patterns and unifies them into a lightweight framework for O-RAN FL. From a security perspective, we focus on threats from FL clients while assuming Byzantine-resilient Polygon PoS consensus and standard cryptographic primitives. Clients may submit low-quality or adversarial metrics, replay or reorder past measurements, or collude to inflate reputation. FL-DApp mitigates these behaviors through role-based access control in `registrationClient`, oracle-signed payloads bound to client and round identifiers, time-to-live (TTL) and freshness checks, and enforcement of a single effective metric per `(client, roundId)` on chain. Key material for CLSPs and the AGSP is assumed to be managed according to operational best practices, while consensus-level attacks or prolonged denial-of-service on the underlying blockchain are out of scope. Protection of local training data and model-update poisoning are likewise delegated to complementary mechanisms

(e.g., secure aggregation, differential privacy, or ZK proofs), which we regard as orthogonal extensions of the artifact.

Our evaluation in this article focuses on blockchain-layer behavior (gas usage, confirmation latency, and the overhead of batched reputation commits) on Polygon Amoy under realistic fee and congestion conditions. Quantifying how alternative reputation policies affect FL convergence, model accuracy, and robustness to adversarial or intermittently participating clients in specific O-RAN tasks is left for future work, using FL-DApp as a reusable trust layer within task-specific FL pipelines. The artifact also enables investigation of cross-deployment consistency (scoring rules, fixed-point encodings, and events/logs), trade-offs between `updateScore()` batch size and gas/latency/reliability (e.g., SLO/ECDF) under varying load and fees, the impact of `topP/thresholding/weighting` on accuracy, participation, and fairness under non-IID data, robustness to noisy/adversarial metrics (including collusion, bribery, and replay) and the role of decay/staking/slashing, and where computation/proofs should reside (e.g., oracles, secure aggregation, ZK attestations) to minimise cost while preserving auditability. FL-DApp is an early-stage reference for batched, auditable reputation updates in cross-provider FL, currently targeting Non-RT deployments and omitting privacy proofs, incentives/slashing, and formal verification. Future work will add configurable policies (e.g., decay, staking/slashing), privacy-preserving attestations, and batching/streaming strategies, with community contributions encouraged.

7. Conclusion and future work

We presented FL-DApp, an open-source artifact providing a lightweight, auditable reputation layer for cross-provider FL in O-RAN. It separates on-chain logic from an off-chain Reputation Manager and performs one batched update per round. A reference deployment on Polygon Amoy includes reproducible evaluation scripts; ECDF results show a ~7 s latency (~86% reliability), supporting seconds-scale SLOs. FL-DApp remains focused on core reputation logic but will evolve to support configurable batching, multi-round scheduling, and broader EVM L2 portability. Planned features include privacy-preserving ingestion (secure aggregation, ZK proofs) and operational safeguards such as staking and slashing for adversarial resilience. Furthermore, an important direction for future work is to integrate FL-DApp with specific FL workloads and adversarial scenarios in O-RAN to quantify how different reputation policies affect model convergence, accuracy, and resilience in multi-operator deployments.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Farhana Javed: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Engin Zeydan:** Writing

– review & editing, Methodology. **Josep Mangues-Bafalluy**: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Interface and contract excerpts

```

1 pragma solidity ^0.8.20;
2
3 event ReputationUpdated(uint32 indexed roundId, address indexed client,
4   ↪ uint256 score);
5
6 interface IReputationScore {
7   function updateScore(uint32 roundId, address[] calldata clients,
8     ↪ uint256[] calldata scores) external;
9   function getReputation(uint32 roundId, address client) external view
10    ↪ returns (uint256);
11 }

```

Listing 4. Public interface excerpt (round-scoped).

```

1 uint256 public constant MAX_SCORE = 1e18;
2 mapping(uint32 => mapping(address => uint256)) public reputation; //
3   ↪ round-scoped
4
5 function updateScore(
6   uint32 roundId,
7   address[] calldata clients,
8   uint256[] calldata scores
9 ) external {
10   uint256 n = clients.length;
11   require(n > 0 && scores.length == n, "LEN_MISMATCH");
12   // require(msg.sender == aggregator, "ONLY_AGGREGATOR");
13   // require(roundState[roundId] != Finalized, "ROUND_FINALIZED");
14   for (uint256 i = 0; i < n; ++i) {
15     uint256 s = scores[i];
16     require(s <= MAX_SCORE, "SCORE_OOB");
17     reputation[roundId][clients[i]] = s;
18   }
19   // emit events as needed
20 }

```

Listing 5. Guard checks for updateScore(): length match and score bounds.

Appendix B. Scripts and tooling

```

1 npx hardhat run scripts/deploy.ts --network polygon
2 npx hardhat sco:bind-oracle --job fetchOracle
3 npx hardhat sco:open-round --round 1
4 node services/oracle-adapter.js --network polygon
5 node services/agsp-repman.js
6 node scripts/register-clients.js \
7   --count 50 --passes 10 \
8   --writeTxt registration_seq_50x10_log.txt \
9   --writeCsv registration_seq_50x10_log.csv
10 node scripts/submit-metrics.js --round 1
11 npx hardhat sco:close-round --round 1 && \
12 node scripts/update-scores.js --round 1 && \
13 npx hardhat sco:finalize-round --round 1

```

Listing 6. Deployment, metric submission, and round finalization commands for one FL-DApp round.

FL Client Registration Data				
Iteration	Address	Gas Used	Cost (MATIC)	Latency (s)
1	0x591F3084a5...b42dC76A	43464	0.00006519600	9.410
1	0xf985876271...5015a687	43464	0.00006519600	9.675
1	0x0abD193402...ce861b4C	43464	0.00006519600	9.333
1	0xb975491825...3ECb0292	43464	0.00006519600	9.742
1	0xF838d9E41c...1d9E4a02	43464	0.00006519600	9.738

The total execution time for registration of clients is: 466.383 s.

Listing 7. Preview of iteration 1 registration log.

Explorer Data: Mined Transactions on FL-DAPP						
Time	Status	Tx Hash	Mempool	Nounce	GasPrice(gwei)	Block #
10:22 AM	MINED	0xc747a421df...	00:00:04	525	61.0	13038643
10:22 AM	MINED	0xf321435593...	00:00:04	524	40.0	13038643
10:22 AM	MINED	0xd127a44cece...	00:00:03	523	40.0	13038632
10:21 AM	MINED	0xa8e8954b485...	00:00:04	522	67.1	13038632
10:21 AM	MINED	0x4dac36ff61e...	00:00:02	521	61.0	13038610
10:21 AM	MINED	0xa08facef479...	00:00:06	520	78.1	13038601
10:20 AM	MINED	0xf057adfccc8...	00:00:05	519	61.0	13038590
10:20 AM	MINED	0x5fa82eb1e60...	00:00:03	518	61.0	13038578
10:19 AM	MINED	0x626f5e804c8...	00:00:04	517	61.0	13038568
10:19 AM	MINED	0x2995bc3bfff...	00:00:03	516	30.0	13038557
10:18 AM	MINED	0xa0147e64be9...	00:00:03	515	25.0	13038535
10:18 AM	MINED	0x5d1647bc23a...	00:00:04	514	67.1	13038525

Listing 8. Mempool explorer log of mined transactions.

```

1 const { JsonRpcProvider } = require("ethers");
2 const provider = new JsonRpcProvider(process.env.ALCHEMY_RPC_URL);
3
4 async function txDelay(txHash, sentAt) {
5   const rc = await provider.getTransactionReceipt(txHash);
6   const block = await provider.getBlock(rc.blockNumber);
7   const minedAt = Number(block.timestamp);
8   const hasSent = sentAt !== undefined && !isNaN(Number(sentAt));
9   const delay = hasSent ? (minedAt - Number(sentAt)) : "NA";
10  const sent = hasSent ? Number(sentAt) : "NA";
11  console.log(` ${txHash}, ${sent}, ${minedAt}, ${delay}`);
12 }
13
14 if (require.main === module) {
15   txDelay(process.argv[2], process.argv[3]).catch(e => { console.error(e);
16     ↪ process.exit(1); });
17 }

```

Listing 9. Utility script to compute inclusion delay from mempool to mined block.

```

1 ALCHEMY_RPC_URL="https://polygon-amoy.g.alchemy.com/v2/..."
2 PRIVATE_KEY="0xfeed...ff"
3 CHAIN_ID=80002
4 # CONTRACT_ADDRESS="0xYourDeployedReputationScore"
    
```

Listing 10. Minimal .env file for Polygon Amoy deployment.

Appendix C. Tables and configuration summaries

Table 2
Core entry points for each component.

Component	Script/interface	Purpose
SMO-Client (CLSP)	train_local.py/inference_nmse.py	Runs local training or inference and outputs NMSE to metrics file.
	publish_metric.py (Oracle Adapter)	Signs and publishes the latest metric to the oracle feed; prints signature and timestamp.
	dapp_submit.py (DApp Adapter)	Handles registration and admin calls (e.g., registerAsClient, policy queries); manages gas, nonce, retries; prints tx status.
Smart Contract Orchestrator (SCO)	openRound, closeRound, finalizeRound	Manages round lifecycle; emits key events and updates on-chain flags.
	getReputation, getRoundInfo	Read-only calls for retrieving scores or round state; useful for dashboards and aggregators.
SMO-Aggregator (AGSP)	open_round.js/finalize_round.js	Initiates and completes training rounds; prints transaction status and gas used.
	aggregate.py (Reputation Manager)	Performs weighted aggregation using top-ranked clients; generates evaluation plots.

Table 3
SCO modules and contracts: persistent state and key write interfaces.

Contract (sol)	Key state (type /name)	Key write
registrationClient	mapping(address->bool)/isClient, mapping(address->bool)/isAggregator, address/admin	registerAsClient(); registerAggregator(addr, username);
fetchOracle	address/oracle, bytes32/feedId, uint32/ttlSec	setOracle(addr); requestNMSE(roundId); fulfill(client, roundId, nmseFixed, scale, ts, signature);
performanceSubmission	mapping(uint32->Round)/rounds, mapping(uint32->mapping(address->bool))/submitted, mapping(uint32->mapping(address->uint256))/nmseFixed, uint32/scale (=1e6)	openRound(roundId, policyHash, selectPct, ttlSec); submitNMSE(roundId, nmseFixed, scale); closeRound(roundId);
reputationCalculation	mapping(address->uint256)/reputation, uint8/selectPct (90)	initializeScores(roundId); updateScore(roundId, clients[], scores[]); finalizeRound(roundId);

Table 4
Reputation module functions: purpose, preconditions, and state mutations (events).

Function	Purpose (round-scoped)	Preconditions → effect (event)
initializeScores(roundId)	Zero per-client scores for the cohort (gas-efficient reset).	Aggregator-only; round <i>Open/Closed</i> but not <i>Finalized</i> → clear/initialize slots. (optional ReputationInit)
updateScore(roundId, clients[], scores[])	Persist off-chain computed fixed-point scores (from NMSE).	Arrays nonempty and equal length; each client registered; values within scale bounds; round not <i>Finalized</i> → set reputation[client] for all. (ReputationUpdated)
finalizeRound(roundId)	Seal the snapshot; prevent further mutation.	Round <i>Closed</i> ; at least one updateScore executed → mark <i>Finalized</i> ; expose snapshot metadata. (RoundFinalized)

Table 5
Required artifacts and configuration for the minimal illustrative run.

Artifact	Example/field	Notes/validation
Environment file	.env with ALCHEMY_RPC_URL, PRIVATE_KEY, NETWORK=amoy	Key not committed; RPC reachable; account funded on Amoy.
Contract addresses	SCD_ADDR, REGISTRY_ADDR (deployed)	Checksum format; match the current network chain ID.
Policy params	selectPct (e.g., 90), ttlSec, policyHash	Validated by openRound; range checks enforced.
Client config	N_CLIENTS, seeds, tiny dataset path	Synthetic or toy set; deterministic seeds optional.
Oracle signer	ORACLE_PUBKEY/feed binding	ECDSA verifies; feedId bound to roundId.
Outputs (generated)	metrics.csv, tx_log.json, accuracy.png	Produced by scripts; used for the composite figure.

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